

Pollen/spikelet sterility scores and other features of local and IRRI CMS lines at Kapurthala.

CMS line	Sterility reaction ^a		Days to flowering	Plant height (cm)			Anther color and shape	Grain type ^b
	Pollen	Spikelet		A line	B line	Percent reduction		
Pb CMS 1A	CS	CS	110	83	102	18.6	Yellowish	LS
Pb CMS 2A	CS	CS	110	89	101	11.9	White shrunken	LS
Pb CMS 3A	CS	CS	104	88	100	12.0	White shrunken	LS
Pb CMS 4A	CS	CS	110	86	105	18.1	White shrunken	LS
Pb CMS 5A	HS	S	106	81	101	19.8	White	LS
Pb CMS 6A	PS	PS	110	85	105	19.0	White	LS
Pb CMS 7A	HS	HS	109	81	100	19.0	White	MM
Pb CMS 8A	CS	CS	104	84	99	15.1	White shrunken	LS
Pb CMS 9A	PF	PS	102	97	108	10.2	Yellowish	LS
Pb CMS 10A	CS	CS	105	85	95	10.5	White shrunken	LS
Pb CMS 11A	CS	CS	112	91	111	18.0	Brownish	LS
Pb CMS 12A	CS	CS	104	72	91	20.9	White shrunken	LS
Pb CMS 13A	CS	CS	110	86	108	20.4	White shrunken	ELS
V20A	CS	CS	73	68	82	17.1	White shrunken	MM
IR58025A	CS	CS	97	73	95	23.1	White shrunken	LS
IR62829A	PS	S	101	70	85	17.6	White shrunken	MS
IR64607A	CS	CS	104	85	106	19.8	White shrunken	LS
IR64608A	CS	CS	104	79	118	33.0	Yellow shrunken	MS
IR66707A	HS	HS	112	86	117	26.5	White shrunken	LS
IR67683A	CS	CS	114	81	111	27.0	White shrunken	LS
IR67684A	PS	PS	100	83	97	14.4	White shrunken	ELS
IR68275A	HS	CS	104	92	105	12.4	Yellow shrunken	MM
IR68280A	PS	PS	114	82	98	16.3	Yellow plump	LS
IR68281A	CS	CS	95	89	104	14.4	White shrunken	LS
IR68886A	PF	PF	105	87	100	13.0	White	LS
IR68887A	HS	S	99	93	117	20.5	Yellowish	MS
IR68888A	CS	CS	88	84	93	9.6	White shrunken	MS
IR68891A	PF	PF	88	92	102	9.8	White shrunken	MM
IR68895A	CS	CS	100	78	100	22.0	Yellowish	LS
IR68897A	PF	PF	98	76	99	23.2	Yellowish	LS
IR68899A	CS	CS	101	83	101	17.8	Yellowish	LS
IR68902A	CS	CS	106	89	104	14.4	White shrunken	LS
IR69628A	CS	CS	103	95	101	5.9	White shrunken	LS

^a Completely sterile (CS) = 100% pollen/spikelet sterility, highly sterile (HS) = 99-99.9%, sterile (S) = 95-98.9%, partially sterile (PS) = 70-94.9%, partially fertile (PF) = <70%, ^bLS = long slender, LM = long medium, ELS = extra long slender, MM = medium medium, MS = medium slender.

Genetically diverse lines included in the study displayed wide variation for days to flowering (73-114). Therefore these lines can be used to develop rice hybrids with desired maturity. The lines Pb CMS 12A, V20A, IR58025A, IR62829A, IR64608A, IR68895A, and IR68897A were typically dwarf in stature (<80 cm). The WA cytoplasm reduced height by 5.9-33.0% compared with the respective maintainer lines, whereas *O. perennis* cytoplasm resulted in a plant height decreased by 26.5% compared with the maintainer IR66707B.

The white anther trait in the completely sterile CMS line is desirable because it facilitates visual discrimination between fertile and sterile plants at anthesis for practical hybrid seed production. Considering male sterility and anther color, Pb CMS 2A, 3A, 4A, 7A, 8A, 10A, 12A, 13A, V20A, IR58025A, IR64607A, IR66707A, IR67683A, IR68281A, IR68888A, IR68902A, and IR69628A are desirable CMS lines. From these, all except Pb CMS 7A, V20A, and IR68888A possess long slender grains. These CMS lines are also being screened for panicle and stigma exertion rate, outcrossing potential, combining ability, and disease resistance, all traits that can render them commercially usable. ■

Comparison of regeneration frequency of green plantlets from in vitro culture of young panicles of wild rice

Guangxuan Tan, Xiaohui Yin, Lihui Shu, Guangchen He, and Lanjie Liao, College of Life Sciences, Wuhan University, Wuhan 430072, China

Wild *Oryza* species compose an important germplasm pool of high level genetic diversity and a number of economically important genes. However, most wild *Oryza* species prove recalcitrant in tissue and cell culture, which is an obstacle to the genetic manipulation of the valuable

germplasm. Recently, we cultured the young panicles of wild rice on different media and confirmed that the young panicles of wild rice have two development tendencies: dedifferentiation and redifferentiation. In both cases, green plantlet regenerations with high frequency were obtained for some species.

Nine species of wild rice were used in the experiments. The young panicles (0.1-1.5 cm in length of the inflorescence) were plated either on the callus-inducing medium containing N6 + 2 mg 2,4-D L⁻¹ + 4.5% sucrose, pH 5.8 (method 1) or on the differentiating medium containing MS + 2 mg 6-BA L⁻¹ + 0.5 mg NAA L⁻¹ + 3% sucrose, pH 5.8

(method 2). In the first culture method, the induced calli for 16 accessions of nine species of wild rice were transferred onto the differentiating medium. Green plantlets were obtained from six species (see table). The genomes of the species with regenerated plantlets were AA, A¹A¹, CC, CCDD and *O. meyeriana* with an unnamed genome. Until now, we have not obtained regenerated plantlets from *O. eichingeri*, *O. punctata*, and *O. brachyantha* via callus redifferentiation. Green spots were observed on the calli of these species. Variation in the regeneration frequency also occurred among the accessions within the species. The regeneration frequency

Plant regeneration frequency from wild rice inflorescence cultured by two different methods. Wuhan, China.

Species	Genome	Origin	No.	Method 1		Method 2			
				Calli transferred (no.)	Regenerated plants (no.)	Regeneration frequency (%)	Panicles cultured (no.)	Regenerated plants (no.)	Regeneration frequency (%)
<i>Oryza rufipogon</i>	AA	China	2	-	-	-	20	18	90.0
			3	8	0	0	-	-	-
			4	18	0	0	22	21	95.5
			5	18	2	11.1	35	26	74.3
			6	13	0	0	15	8	50.0
				17	10	58.8	17	13	76.5
<i>O. longstaminata</i>	A ¹ A ¹	Stolon Philippines		15	0	0	-	-	-
				20	4	20.0	-	-	-
<i>O. punctata</i>	BBCC	India		12	0	0	-	-	-
<i>O. officinalis</i>	CC	China		14	0	0	-	-	-
				16	0	0	37	0	0
				34	10	29.4	-	-	-
<i>O. eichingeri</i>	CC	Sri Lanka		15	0	0	30	12	40.0
<i>O. alta</i>	CCDD	Brazil		18	10	55.6	27	18	66.7
<i>O. latifolia</i>	CCDD	Mexico		21	3	14.3	23	12	52.2
<i>O. brachyantha</i>	FF	Zambia		15	0	0	-	-	-
<i>O. meyeriana</i>	?	China		24	14	58.3	15	12	80.0

^a - not tested.

was only 11.1% in the normal type of *O. rufipogon* (number 5), but 58.8% in the stolon type of the same species.

In the second culture method, plantlets regenerated directly from the young panicles of wild rice that were cultured on the differentiating medium. Six species including 10

accessions were tested. Plantlets were obtained from five species except *O. officinalis*. The regeneration frequency was generally higher in this method than in the method via callus differentiation. Compared with plantlet differentiation via callus, direct regeneration of young panicles was much simpler

and the time needed shorter. Direct regeneration might present less risk to somatic variation than is common in in vitro tissue culture of the plant. Therefore, this method has potential in micropropagation, genetic manipulation, and cryopreservation of *Oryza* germplasm. ■

Determination of suitable time to select trisomics induced from anther culture of autotetraploid rice

Wu Minsheng, Genetic and Breeding Department, China Agricultural University, Beijing 100094, China

Use of primary trisomics has played an important role in genetics and breeding of rice. A great number of trisomics could be induced through anther culture of autotetraploid rice. In earlier work, trisomics of rice selected according to auricle distances from -2.5 cm to + 2.5 cm resulted in low selection efficiency. This paper reports on an efficient time to select trisomics.

Relationship between auricle distance and frequency of anthers in various phases.

	Metaphase		Metaphase	Abnormal
	Trisomic	Diploid	(%)	(%)
Auricle distance (cm) ^a	-1.5 to + 1.5		-	-
Observed number (bottle)	20	59	68.1	31.9

^aDistance between auricle of the flag leaf and that of the next leaf from the flag leaf.

From 116 bottle anthers of young panicles of autotetraploid rice, we selected 100 panicles randomly per bottle. The results were as follows: 1) when auricle distance was from -1.5 cm to + 1.5 cm, all anthers were in metaphase and trisomics or diploids could be determined; 2) when auricle distance was from -2.5 cm to + 2.5 cm,

only 68.1% of the anthers were in metaphase; and 3) when auricle distance was from -2.5 cm to -1.5 cm or from + 1.5 cm to + 2.5 cm, no anthers were in metaphase (see table).

We concluded that an auricle distance from -1.5 cm to + 1.5 cm was better than from -2.5 cm to + 2.5 cm for selecting trisomics. ■